

Optimum Portfolio Construction Using Riskfolio-Lib in Python

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Abstract

The construction of an optimal portfolio is a critical component of financial decision-making, aiming to maximize returns while minimizing risk. This paper presents an empirical analysis of portfolio optimization using the Riskfolio-Lib, a Python library designed for financial portfolio optimization and risk management. The implementation uses historical stock data of seven technology firms to construct and analyze an efficient portfolio. We integrate the theoretical framework of Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT) with practical programming, detailing the results and visualization of key outputs.

Keywords:

Portfolio Optimization, Riskfolio Library, Mean-Variance Optimization, Efficient Frontier, Sharpe Ratio, Asset Allocation, Risk Management, Python for Finance

1. Introduction

Investment portfolio optimization aims to balance risk and return effectively. Introduced by Harry Markowitz in 1952, Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT) forms the cornerstone of this approach. The Riskfolio-Lib leverages Python's computational efficiency and MPT's principles to provide a robust framework for constructing and analyzing optimal portfolios. This paper demonstrates portfolio construction with a focus on:

1. Risk-return trade-offs.
2. Efficient frontier analysis.
3. Maximizing the Sharpe Ratio.

2. Theoretical Framework

2.1 Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT)

MPT optimizes a portfolio's allocation by diversifying assets to minimize variance (risk) for a given level of expected return. Key concepts include:

- Risk (Variance): Measures the variability of returns.
- Expected Return: The weighted sum of expected returns of portfolio assets.
- Efficient Frontier: The set of portfolios offering the highest expected return for a defined level of risk.
- Sharpe Ratio: Measures risk-adjusted return and is given by:

$$\text{Sharpe Ratio} = (E[R_p] - R_f) / \sigma_p$$

where $E[R_p]$ is portfolio return, R_f is the risk-free rate, and σ_p is portfolio risk.

2.2 Risk Measures

In this study, we use Mean-Variance (MV) optimization, minimizing portfolio variance while considering the Sharpe ratio as the objective.

2.3 Riskfolio-Lib

Riskfolio-Lib is a Python library designed for financial portfolio optimization. It provides tools to analyze risk, return, and other metrics, and supports various risk measures and portfolio models (e.g., mean-variance, mean-CVaR).

3. Methodology

3.1 Data Collection

We utilize historical adjusted closing prices of seven technology stocks (NVIDIA, Microsoft, Amazon, Tesla, Meta, Apple, and Alphabet) retrieved via the yfinance library for the period 2019-11-18 to 2024-11-18.

3.2 Portfolio Optimization

The steps in the optimization process are:

1. Calculate Returns: Compute daily percentage changes.
2. Portfolio Model: Classic mean-variance (MV) optimization.
3. Objective Function: Maximize Sharpe Ratio.
4. Risk-Free Rate (Rf): Set to 0 for simplicity and also as it is not relevant for our analysis.

3.3 Visualizations

Key outputs include:

- Portfolio composition pie chart.
- Efficient frontier with risk-adjusted return ratios.
- Allocation across efficient frontier points.

The optimum weights as output were given as:

weights	
AAPL	1.054269e-01
AMZN	4.241068e-09
GOOGL	1.026606e-08
META	7.569935e-09
MSFT	9.866662e-09
NVDA	6.773718e-01
TSLA	2.172013e-01

4. Implementation

4.1 Python Code

The following code outlines the implementation:

```
1 import yfinance as yf
2 import riskfolio as rp
3 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
4 import warnings
5
6 warnings.filterwarnings("ignore")
7
8 # Data Setup
9 start = "2019-11-18"
10 end = "2024-11-18"
11 assets = ["NVDA", "MSFT", "AMZN", "TSLA", "META", "AAPL", "GOOGL"]
12
13 data = yf.download(assets, start=start, end=end)['Adj Close']
14 returns = data.pct_change().dropna()
15
16 # Portfolio Optimization
17 port = rp.Portfolio(returns=returns)
18 method_mu = 'hist'
19 method_cov = 'hist'
20 port.assets_stats(method_mu=method_mu, method_cov=method_cov)
21
22 # Optimization
23 w = port.optimization(model='Classic', rm='MV', obj='Sharpe', rf=0, l=0, hist=True)
24
25 # Visualizations
26 rp.plot_pie(w=w, title="Optimum Portfolio", others=0.05, cmap='tab20')
27 plt.show()
28
29 frontier = port.efficient_frontier(model='Classic', rm='MV', points=50, rf=0, hist=True)
30 rp.plot_frontier(w_frontier=frontier, mu=port.mu, cov=port.cov, returns=returns, rf=0, cmap='viridis', w=w)
31 plt.show()
32
```

4.2 Output

1. Optimal Portfolio Composition: The pie chart (Figure 1) shows the asset weights for the optimized portfolio.

Figure 1: Optimum Portfolio Composition

2. Efficient Frontier: Figure 2 illustrates the trade-off between risk and return, with the optimal portfolio highlighted.

Figure 2: Efficient Frontier

3. Asset Structure: Figure 3 demonstrates asset allocation across different frontier points.

Figure 3: Efficient Frontier's Asset Structure

4. Comprehensive Risk Report: Figure 4 provides detailed risk measures, returns distribution, and drawdown metrics.

Riskfolio-Lib Report

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	Values	(Return - MAR)/Risk
Profitability and Other Inputs		
Mean Return (1)	105.0050%	
Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR)	84.4623%	
Minimum Acceptable Return (MAR) (1)	0.0000%	
Significance Level	5.0000%	
Risk Measures based on Returns		
Standard Deviation (2)	56.5304%	1.857494
Mean Absolute Deviation (MAD) (2)	41.4092%	2.535791
Semi Standard Deviation (2)	40.0714%	2.620444
First Lower Partial Moment (FLPM) (2)	18.1201%	5.794941
Second Lower Partial Moment (SLPM) (2)	37.3149%	2.814025
Value at Risk (VaR) (2)	88.0607%	1.192415
Conditional Value at Risk (CVaR) (2)	122.7545%	0.855406
Entropic Value at Risk (EVaR) (2)	140.1372%	0.749301
Tail Gini of Losses (TG) (2)	192.8607%	0.544460
Relativistic Value at Risk (RLVaR) (2)	264.9384%	0.396337
Worst Realization (2)	341.7942%	0.307217
Skewness	0.01936	
Kurtosis	3.19081	
Risk Measures based on Drawdowns (3)		
Ulcer Index (UCI)	21.1913%	4.955106
Average Drawdown (ADD)	12.4558%	8.430221
Drawdown at Risk (DaR)	52.7366%	1.991120
Conditional Drawdown at Risk (CDaR)	59.3185%	1.770190
Entropic Drawdown at Risk (EDaR)	62.4641%	1.681044
Relativistic Drawdown at Risk (RLDaR)	65.0295%	1.614728
Max Drawdown (MDD)	72.0100%	1.458200

(1) Annualized, multiplied by 365

(2) Annualized, multiplied by $\sqrt{365}$

(3) Based on uncompounded cumulated returns

Figure 4: Detailed Report

5. Results and Discussion

5.1 Portfolio Allocation

The portfolio's weights are heavily skewed toward NVIDIA (67.7%), followed by Tesla (21.7%) and Apple (10.5%). This allocation reflects these assets' historical risk-return profiles and their contribution to the overall portfolio Sharpe ratio.

5.2 Efficient Frontier Analysis

The efficient frontier indicates portfolios offering maximum returns for a given risk. The optimal portfolio, marked with a red star, balances risk and return effectively.

5.3 Risk Assessment

Key metrics from the risk report include:

- Annualized Standard Deviation: 56.53%.
- Sharpe Ratio: 1.857 (indicating a favorable risk-adjusted return).
- Max Drawdown (MDD): -72.01%, reflecting significant historical drawdowns.

5.4 Practical Implications

Investors can use Riskfolio-Lib to construct data-driven portfolios and make informed decisions. However, results depend on historical data assumptions, which may not always predict future performance.

6. Conclusion

This paper demonstrates how Riskfolio-Lib facilitates optimal portfolio construction using MPT principles. Through Python programming, we maximize the Sharpe ratio, analyze efficient frontier dynamics, and visualize portfolio allocations. Future research could explore dynamic portfolio optimization techniques and alternative risk measures like Conditional Value-at-Risk (CVaR).

References

1. Markowitz, H. (1952). 'Portfolio Selection.' Journal of Finance.
2. Riskfolio-Lib Documentation: <https://riskfolio-lib.readthedocs.io>
3. yFinance Documentation: <https://pypi.org/project/yfinance>